

Fast and Robust rover Navigation with Convolutional Neural Networks: FARNAV, an AI feasibility study

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With the upcoming space missions for exploration in Mars and returning to the Moon, the need of autonomy regarding rover navigation is discernible. In this regard, Airbus Defence and Space has been developing Guidance Navigation and Control (GNC) algorithms for missions like ESA's ExoMars and the Sample Fetch Rover. While those classical rigid algorithms work for their target missions, some challenges arise regarding their flexibility for future applications. Aspects like run time and robustness to camera shifts and other miscalibration effects need to be considered, which are very common e.g. due to harsh launcher, lander and rover operations.

Thus, Airbus has taken a different approach with FARNAV (Fast And Robust NAVigation): an image based Deep Learning solution to create navigation maps (NavMaps). FARNAV's final goal is to outperform the classical GNC stack computer vision algorithm. This paper is our first step into proving the feasibility of creating NavMaps with Convolutional Neural Networks. The tested architectures and challenges encountered when applying Deep Learning to the problem are analysed and the results discussed, concluding that the problem is solvable by the AI. The results open the path to further analysis on the integration and algorithm development towards its final goal.

1 Introduction

Although Airbus Guidance Navigation and Control (GNC) rover algorithms are space qualified, they are designed with the assumption that inputs (pair of images acquired via stereo camera) are accurately calibrated with well characterised errors. This was proven to be challenging for a system that experiences rocket start, inter-planetary cruise, planetary landing and operation in an all-terrain environment. These harsh environmental conditions degrade the camera calibration and characterisation and therefore incorporate disturbances and noises into the input images of the navigation algorithm. Moreover, classical solutions, designed to fit deep space On-Board Computers (OBC) processing power budgets, are typically as rigid

as possible for particular mission constraints. Handling the rover safety and its interaction with the planetary surface implies substantial computational cost.

The classical navigation algorithm is designed to allow rovers to navigate through terrain (e.g. avoid rocks, slopes etc). Its logic is shown in Figure 1 and its full description can be found in [1]. The whole pipeline works with three stereo-pair inputs, computing the disparity maps of each and, from there, the terrain model. Between this step and the final full Navigation Map (NavMap), a set of cost functions is added to evaluate the traversability and risk of each region, adding some safety margins. This algorithm is however prone to camera shift and other miscalibration effects camera dynamics (blur) and has limited accuracy. It also takes a long time to run (minutes on target processor of 100MHz).

In this regard, FARNAV (Fast And Robust NAVigation) aims to tackle both problems with a unique solution, integrating all processing steps and moving the computational load to the on-ground training process through Deep Learning. Neural Networks (NN) provide efficient mechanisms to compensate for hardware uncertainties or noises and are flexible, i.e., the same solution can be applied to different environments. For the NN to be able to extrapolate and achieve a sense of logic and perception, one needs to provide all the range of environments in the datasets in training. This provides long term benefits, as implementations that have been validated once can be reused and only need to be requalified performance-wise for the new data perimeter; which creates a generic, iteratively improved product.

This paper is our first step towards this possible solution, that studies the feasibility of FARNAV to solve NavMaps with Deep Learning. As a first approach, only one stereo-pair will be taken as input and a binary NavMap will be outputted (traversable or non-traversable). Also note, that the scope of this study is to show its feasibility under artificially generated images. This is done due to the lack of sufficient real

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Figure 1: Classical rover GNC algorithm architecture. The whole diagram can be found in [1].

images with the same camera features as the one of target missions, in which the classical GNC algorithm is based, in order to train a NN on it. The obtained trained architecture is also tested on a small set of real images from real-world field trials.

1.1 FARNAV under an AI point of view

Machine Learning models offer a potential solution for our problem. Indeed, some examples in the literature show the potential of this technique applied to navigation [2] [3] [4]. However, as any engineering solution, it also comes with challenges. The main identified are 1) lack of representativeness on the data during training and validation, 2) overfitting and 3) inference into an OBC for space flight operation.

For space computer vision (CV) applications, real images from celestial bodies as the Moon or Mars are

limited and the ones available do not normally coincide with the camera features of the new missions, plus these need to be diverse within the range of operation. Due to this limitation, FARNAV is trained under a synthetic dataset, created using an Airbus rendering tool. Our objective in this paper is to train a model under this, that is able to produce NavMaps when synthetic images are inputted. Our final objective will be, in a Sim2Real paradigm, to develop a model that is able to detect the patterns in real images when trained under a synthetic dataset. Under this goal, the model is also tested against target mission context field trial images, so called “real images”, taken on Earth, which are a decent substitute to real Mars / Moon images.

The image generation tool allows to be specific on the camera features and offers scalability in terms of features in the terrain and types of miscalibration and noises. This also addresses the overfitting challenge, as it ensures features diversity in the training set. Full connectivity among nodes in NNs may also lead to overfitting. In this sense, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), first introduced by [5], achieve a more efficient architecture for pattern recognition with fewer connections and parameters, thanks to its biological inspiration from the animal visual cortex [6]. Moreover, their ability to perform with limited memory and hardware capability make them a good candidate under the third presented challenge. Although the first application of CNNs was presented in 1995 by LeCun et. al. [7], their popularity for image classification did not arise till the 2000s, thanks to the computer development, the increase of labelled data and the appearance of better algorithms [8].

2 Modelling and analysis

2.1 Overall Architecture

As a first approach, a single U-Net was used to transform from the stereo-pair directly to the navigation map. U-Net is a type of semantic segmentation CNN model that was first introduced in [3]. However, it was found that this was too ambitious for a single network to handle, as it would be responsible for recreating the entire classical algorithm pipeline: estimate the distance and size of the terrain features, perform a spatial mapping from the image to a top down (conic) view of the visible terrain, determine whether or not any given feature is a hazard or traversable and, finally, dilate any hazardous regions to provide a safety margin for the rover. An attempt was made to reduce the overfitting using both dropout and L2 regularisation, but both attempts were unsuccessful.

Figure 2: FARNAV architecture: chosen architecture with single intermediate input.

The architecture was redesigned to improve accuracy and mitigate against overfitting. Due to the complexity of translating the stereo images directly to navigation maps (see Figure 4) with a single model, a two-step approach was taken instead where a dedicated network -Intermediate Map Model (IMM)- would be responsible for the initial step of generating the disparity map (or depth map) and a secondary network -Navigation Map Model (NMM)- would be responsible for converting the disparity/depth map to the final NavMap (reusing the original U-net). Separating the problem into two separate networks was found to improve performance. It was also found that passing the original stereo images to the NMM along with the disparity/depth map would result in overfitting.

Finally, the approach was taken to include only the output of the IMM as an input to the NMM which significantly improved the overfitting issues encountered. Thus, it was decided to implement a chained model approach for the end to end architecture (see Figure 2). The additional IMM provides two key benefits: 1) it transforms the inputs into a format similar to that used to calculate the NavMap in the classical solution from which the ground truth labels are derived and 2) it transforms the input into a common representation for both real and synthetic images therefore supporting the Sim2Real training paradigm.

The team decided to focus the development of the NMM, while using open-source pre-trained models for the IMM, as an interim solution, for the sake of testing the feasibility of the architecture. These models are open source and pre-trained for the task of either monocular depth estimation (single input image) or disparity map generation, from rectified stereo image pairs. The two different open source pre-trained models that have been tested for the IMM are: a) MonoDepth model from [9] and b) Disparity model Uni-match [10]. For the NMM, a FARNAV specific configuration of the U-Net architecture has been developed and is trained exclusively with the outputs from the Intermediate Map Model applied to our synthetic dataset.

2.2 Inputs and outputs of FARNAV

2.2.1 Inputs

Datasets are obtained from two sources: a simulated (synthetic) environment and real world images (from Earth analogues). Under a Sim2Real study, this project aims to train the algorithm primarily with synthetic data but test it on real images. This is an end to end solution, from raw images to final NavMaps, simplifying the navigation to the image translation problem for which well studied and exercised Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) architectures can be applied.

The synthetic images are generated via an Airbus 3D scene rendering tool and can produce ideal images with no imperfections or imperfect images including camera translation and rotational misalignments. The real world images are taken from real-world field trials. All images are fed through the classical rover algorithm in order to produce the (ground truth) dataset labels.

2.2.2 Outputs

The output of FARNAV is a NavMap, the last step in Figure 1 shows the composition of the different NavMaps as the rover traverses through the unknown terrain. In the figure below, a clear NavMap is shown, i.e., the output of FARNAV when there is no hazard on the seen terrain. This clear NavMap is used as mask for the BCM metric explained in the next section. Some examples of NavMaps are also shown in Figure 4.

Figure 3: NavMap, output of FARNAV, when there is no hazard. This is used as mask for one of the metrics.

Figure 4: FARNAV inputs and outputs: examples of synthetic ideal (left) and real (right).

Inside the NavMap we have two classes (note that the last two are categorised as the same, in black): 1) Traversable: area is safe to traverse (white), 2a) Non-traversable: area contains objects that cannot be traversed (within a safety radius) (black) and 2b) Not Visible: no information about this area of the terrain (not seen within input images, black).

2.3 Metrics of the analysis

Two independent metrics are used to evaluate the overall performance: 1) IOU (Intersection Over Union) and 2) Binary Confusion Matrix (BCM).

The IOU assesses how accurately the hazard areas are being predicted and is an independent metric. It is only assessed for the subset of images where a hazard is positively detected in prediction and truth.

The BCM is binary, categorising the images into: a) does not contain hazard (if <5% of pixels inside the mask are non-traversable, when a mask is applied to show the visible region only) or b) contains hazard otherwise (if $\geq 5\%$ of pixels inside the mask are non-traversable, after applying the mask). This metric is a way of rapidly and approximately detecting false positives (wrongly predicted by the model but safe) and false negatives (worst case, as the NavMap shows an area not having hazard, when it is in reality non-traversable).

3 Results

The training was performed using 8525 synthetic ideal images with their corresponding ground truths, output from the classical algorithm. The model has

then been tested on 1280 synthetic ideal, 117 real and 594 synthetic imperfect images. An example of FARNAV inputs and outputs is shown in Figure 4 for ideal synthetic (left) and real (right) inputs: on the top left, the stereo pair of the terrain visible to the rover; top right, disparity map output of the IMM and input to the NMM; down left, ground truth from the classical algorithm; and down right, FARNAV’s NavMap output.

The best results were achieved with the chained architecture with the pre-trained disparity model Unimatch as IMM, and our customised U-Net model as NMM. Table 1 shows the BCM and the average IOU (for the images that include hazard) for this architecture.

Images	\exists hazard	Data points	Avg IOU	True [%]	False [%]
Synthetic ideal	Yes	1098	0.71	91.8	8.2
	No	182	-	73.6	26.4
Synthetic imperfect	Yes	492	0.68	94.1	5.9
	No	102	-	62.7	37.3
Real	Yes	16	0.56	81.3	18.8
	No	106	-	65.1	34.9

Table 1: Results in terms of BCM and average IOU.

4 Discussion

This paper has shown the feasibility of creating navigation maps (NavMaps) with a Deep Learning solution consisting of a chained model of CNNs. The results on Table 1 show to be promising overall. Focusing on the most significant metric, the average IOU, not only the targeted synthetic ideal images scored highly with a 71%, but also the synthetic imperfect scored surprisingly high and close to the latter with a 68%. Although there is a window of improvement, mainly on the real images, which scored the lowest on IOU with a 56%, it has to be highlighted that the synthetic ideal case was the scope of this first analysis, and also the only ones used during training of the NMM.

The main challenge encountered when assessing the feasibility of creating NavMaps with CNNs is the dilation, i.e., the special mapping between input image looking to the front of the rover and the NavMap seen from above the terrain. This dilation seems to be better captured with the chained model approached, and could be improved by providing a more granular classification of terrain classes.

Analysing the BCM metric, which gives an approximate idea of the true/false positives and negatives, on the synthetic ideal images, the well predicted cases (91.8% of true positives and 73.6% of true negatives) are quite above the bad ones (8.2% of false positives and 26.4% of false negatives). This is still true even for the synthetic imperfect case. There is room for improvement on the false negatives (26.4%), when the algorithm detects "no hazard" but it is risky to traverse. We propose as a next step to switch to a multi-class model, predicting 4 different classes inside the NavMap to avoid confusion between the non-visible and the non-traversable regions.

Another way to avoid having false negatives is collect various sets of stereo pairs in different timeframes and positions. This is a future task that will anyway need to be implemented to create the full path planning, as showed at the bottom of Figure 1. In this way, the rover will have several NavMaps outputs of the same area and would take the worst case scenario, which could increase the false positives, but decrease the false negatives, thus, being a safer approach.

Using a chained model approach has shown promising results in applying the model pipeline, trained exclusively on simulated images, to real world images (Sim2Real). However the best performing IMM tested (the disparity model) still has a scope for improvement on accuracy when used in the end to end pipeline. In addition the Intermediate Map Models used for the purpose of these tests has a high infer-

ence time, which may render it incompatible for the project requirements on lower specification hardware.

One recommended next step would be to investigate how to train our own depth or stereo disparity model, in order to meet the accuracy, speed and resource requirements of the FARNAV project. Once developed, this model could then be adapted, with some modification, for other navigation and robotics use cases. A second recommended next step would be to improve the synthetic dataset with images with more realistic features, which the Airbus rendering tool team is already working on, to improve post training performance on real terrains scenarios.

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